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Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY TO ASSESS THE RITUXIMAB EFFECTS
AND SURVIVAL OF THE DIFFUSED LARGE B-CELL
LYMPHOMA PATIENTS MANAGED AT TERTIARY CANCER
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Objective: To decide the effect of Rituximab and worldwide prognostic record score on survival in diffuse vast B-cell lymphoma patients.

Method: The review examines was directed at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (January to June 2017) and involved record of patients with diffuse vast B-cell lymphoma. Benchmark worldwide prognostic list score arrange at introduction were noted and the records were isolated into two gatherings An and B based on the sort of chemotherapy. SPSS was utilized for factual investigation.

Results: Of the 93 patients in the investigation whose record tables were looked into, 54(58%) were men. Generally speaking middle age was 43 years (go: 18 – 76). Stages at introduction were arranging I 14 (15.1%), organize II 41 (44.1%), organize III 20 (21.5%) and arrange IV 18 (19.4%). Universal prognostic list chance categorization was okay 59 (63.4%), low middle of the road hazard 23 (24.7%), high halfway hazard 10 (10.8%) and high hazard 1 (1.1%). There were 31 (33%) patients in Group An and 62 (67%) in Group B. Middle follow-up was 3.9 years (go: 1.2 – 6.1). Generally speaking survival at 4 years was 66.4%; for Group A 65.3% and for Group B 66.7% ($p < 0.4$). Based on hazard classifications, generally speaking, survival was factually critical ($p < 0.001$) between the gatherings.

Conclusion: International prognostic record hazard categorization had a measurably a huge effect on survival. In any case, there was no proof of a huge survival advantage between sorts of chemotherapy. Further controlled preliminaries are required in such a manner.

Keywords: Diffuse large B cell lymphoma, Rituximab, Outcome, Survival, Chemotherapy, Extra Nodal.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diffuse large B cell lymphoma (DLBCL) is a heterogeneous infection as far as morphology, conduct and hereditary qualities. It is the commonest histological subtype of Non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL), representing 25% – 40% of all NHL cases [1 – 3]. It is named a forceful kind of lymphoma [1]. Median age at introduction is 64 years with slight male power. The clinical introduction is variable and reliant on the site of contribution. Most patients present with nodal extension and B side effects (weight reduction, fever, soaking night sweats) [2, 4]. Extranodal infection (gastrointestinal, liver, lung, bosom) is available in 40% of cases [5 – 7]. Most cases (60%) present with cutting edge arrange (i.e. can't be contained in one radiation field), with bone marrow association in 30% of cases and can give harsh histology like follicular lymphoma [8]. DLBCL emerges from developing B cell taking after centroblasts or immunoblasts with the nearness of B cell antigens on immunohistochemistry i.e. (CD19, CD20, CD22, and CD79a) and additionally CD45 on tumour cells. Utilizing quality articulation profiling (GEP) by methods for deoxyribonucleic corrosive (DNA) microarray innovation, DLBCL has been subdivided into germinal focus DLBCL and non-germinal focus DLBCL [9].

In 1993, the International prognostic record (IPI) was proposed which predicts the survival of patients with NHL. It comprises of five components: age >60 years, serum lactate dehydrogenase (S.LDH), and execution status >2, extranodal destinations >1, and phase of ailment III-IV. Utilizing IPI, four prognostic gatherings are framed relying upon the quantity of hazard factors present, generally safe gathering (LR) with 0 – 1 prognostic components, low middle of the road chance gathering (LIR) with 2 prognostic variables, high halfway hazard gathering (HIR) with 3 elements, and high hazard gathering (HR) with 4 – 5 factors. Five-year survival utilizing the IPI prognostic gatherings has been accounted for to be: 73%, 51%, 43% and 26% for the four gatherings respectively [10].

Age-balanced IPI is utilized for patients with age <60 years in which all the above components are incorporated aside from age and extranodal locales. One point is given to each factor so the aggregate score ranges from 0 to 3 with LR score 0, LIR score 1, HIR 2, and HR score 3. Five-year in general survival (OS) is 83%, 96%, 46% and 32% respectively [10].

As of late, upgraded IPI—National Comprehensive Cancer Network-IPI (NCCN-IPI) has been proposed

in which all elements which a piece of unique IPI were were utilized yet further portrayal of age, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) and extranodal locales are proposed [11]. The first change was in age assemble i.e. <40y 0 points, 41-60y 1 point, 61-75y 2 and >75y 3. The second change was in the LDH proportion (LDH-R) i.e. LDH-R <1 0 scores, LDH-R >1-3 score 1, LDH-R >3 scores 2. The third change was in extranodal destinations with 1 score being given to lymphomatous association in bone marrow, focal sensory system (CNS) liver, gastrointestinal (GI) tract and lung. The hazard gatherings, all things considered, are LR (0-1 score), LIR (2 – 3 score), HIR (4 – 5 score) and HR >6. The five-year OS for the four gatherings has been accounted for to be 96%, 82%, 64% and 33% respectively [11].

Poor survival in patients with age >60 could be because of numerous co-morbidities, and poor resistance to chemotherapy. In addition, an ongoing report demonstrated that enacted B cell (ABC) DLBCL is progressively common in seniority which conveys poor prognosis [12].

Over-articulation of c-MYC and B-cell lymphoma 2 (BCL-2) by immunohistochemistry has indicated poor survival in the wake of being treated with Rituximab-based chemotherapy. Moreover, change in p53 likewise results in poor OS [14]. An investigation has proposed two quality scores (TGS) utilizing articulation of tumour cell biomarker LIM area just 2 (LMO2) with miniaturized scale condition marker tumour rot factor (TNF) receptor super relative 9 (TNFRSF9) to anticipate result in DLBCL, yet this needs further validation [15].

Chemotherapy with or without radiation was the standard of consideration for the treatment of DLBCL before the expansion of Rituximab hostile to CD20 counteracting agent in the administration of this sickness. DLBCL is treated with a blend of treatment methodology i.e. chemotherapy and radiation treatment relying on the illness degree. Anthracycline-based chemotherapy comprising of Cyclophosphamide, Doxorubicin, Vincristine and Prednisolone (CHOP) is the most generally utilized and suggested treatment for DLBCL with 3-year OS of 52% [16]. After the presentation of against CD20 monoclonal counteracting agent, Rituximab is utilized in the mix with chemotherapy (Chemoimmunotherapy R-CHOP). Concentrates from the Western world recommend that the survival of patients with DLBCL has enhanced essentially and chemoimmunotherapy is the present standard of care [17].

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The review examines was directed at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (January to June 2017) and involved record of patients with diffuse vast B-cell lymphoma. Information gathering was done through the modernized database framework. Patient's restorative record number, age and sexual orientation were recorded. Standard pathology reports, processed tomography (CT) examine reports and bone marrow biopsies were surveyed. Ann Arbor organizing was utilized to arrange the illness. Serum LDH, execution status, bone marrow contribution and kind of chemotherapy were likewise recorded. Based on the information, IPI hazard categorization was finished. Information was examined utilizing SPSS. OS was determined from the date of enlistment to the last

date of development or demise. OS was assessed utilizing Kaplan Meier survival bends which were thought about utilizing the log-rank test [18, 19].

RESULTS:

Of the 93 patients in the examination whose records were audited, 54 (58%) were men. By and large middle age was 43 years (go: 18 – 76). Stages at introduction were arranging I 14 (15.1%), organize II 41 (44.1%), organize III 20 (21.5%) and organize IV 18 (19.4%). IPI chance arrangement was LR 59 (63.4%), LIR 23 (24.7%), HIR 10 (10.8%) and HR 1 (1.1%). Slash chemotherapy Group A had 31 (33%) patients, while R-CHOP Group B had 62 (67%).

Table – I: Clinicopathological characteristics of patients with DLBCL

Characteristics		Number (93)	Percentage
Gender	Male	54	58
	Female	39	42
Current Status	Alive	63	67.7
	Dead	18	19.4
	Follow-up Lost	12	12.9
Presentation Stage	I	14	15.1
	II	41	44.1
	III	20	21.5
	IV	18	19.4
Bone Marrow Involvement	Yes	4	4.3
	No	89	95.7
IPI Risk Group	Low Risk	59	63.4
	Low Intermediate Risk	23	24.7
	High Intermediate Risk	10	10.8
	High Risk	1	1.1
Chemotherapy Type	CHOP (Group - I)	31	33
	R-CHOP (Group - II)	62	67
Chemotherapy Response	CR (Complete Remission)	74	79.6
	PR (Partial Recovery)	9	9.7
	SD (Stable Disease)	3	3.2
	PD (Progressive Disease)	7	7.5

Table – II: Characteristic of Group – I & II

Chemotherapy Type		CHOP - R (Group - I)		CHOP (Group - II)	
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Presentation Stage	Localized	18	58	37	59.67
	Advanced	13	41.93	25	40.31
IPI Risk Group	Low Risk	18	58	41	66.1
	Low Intermediate Risk	8	25	15	24.1
	High Intermediate Risk	4	12.9	16	9.6
	High Risk	1	3.2	0	0
Chemotherapy Response	CR (Complete Remission)	24	77.4	50	80.6
	PR (Partial Recovery)	3	9.6	6	9.6
	SD (Stable Disease)	0	0	3	4.8
	PD (Progressive Disease)	4	12.9	3	4.8

As per IPI scores in Group A, there were 18 (58.06%), 8 (25.80%), 4 (12.90%) and 1 (3.2%) patients in LR, LIR, HIR and HR classification separately. In Group B, there were 41 (66.12%) patients in LR, 15 (24.19%) in LIR, 6 (9.6%) in HIR, while there was no patient with HR qualities. Consolidative radiation treatment was utilized in 15 (16%) patients; 7 (46.66%) in R-CHOP gathering and 8 (53.33%) in the CHOP gathering. Patients were given at least four and greatest eight cycles of chemotherapy.

Middle follow-up was 3.9 years (extend: 1.2 – 6.1). At the season of examination, 63 (68%) were alive, 18 (19%) were dead and 12 (12.9%) had been lost to development. Middle survival for all patients was not come to. Kaplan Meir evaluated OS at 4 years in both gatherings was 66.4%. At 4 years, OS for Group and Group B were 66.3% and 66.7% ($p=0.4$). At 4 years, OS for LR, LIR, HIR/HR bunches were 79.2%, 54% and 27%, individually and it was measurably noteworthy ($p<0.001$).

DISCUSSION:

The review contemplates included to learning accessible DLBCL, which is the most widely recognized sort of NHL worldwide and there is some worry about the rising number of patients with this

forceful nature of sickness in our population [20]. CHOP chemotherapy has been the standard first-line chemotherapy for quite a few years with finish reaction rate (CRR) of 41%, 3-year illness free survival (DFS) of 41% and 3-year OS of 54% [16]. In GELA preliminary, blend of against CD20 immunizer and CHOP chemotherapy indicated survival advantage in a patient with age >60 years with 5-year OS of 58% in RCHOP versus 45% in CHOP alone, with no clinical huge lethality after including Rituximab with CHOP chemotherapy [21, 22].

In 2006, MInT preliminary was led in more youthful patient age <60 years. Adding Rituximab to CHOP chemotherapy brought about increment of 3-year occasion free survival (EFS) to 79% in R-CHOP gathering and a half in CHOP gathering. So also, 3-year OS was 93% in R-CHOP versus 84% in CHOP. The refreshing result for MInT preliminary has been distributed in 2011, which indicates better 6-year EFS in patients treated with R-CHOP i.e. 74.3% versus 55.8% in CHOP group [23].

The job of maintains Rituximab after R-CHOP blend was tended to in 2006, and demonstrated no enhancement in disappointment free survival (FFS). Notwithstanding, FFS was enhanced by Using

maintains Rituximab after CHOP chemotherapy [24]. IPI has been approved to foresee survival in patients with DLBCL in the pre-Rituximab period. An examination to assess the utility of IPI amid Rituximab time investigated information from three preliminaries and found that IPI still remains a critical device to foresee EFS, DFS and OS in each of the four gatherings, while Rituximab essentially enhances result in all gatherings of IPI [25].

In our examination, the middle age at introduction was 43 years, which is more youthful than the Western world with male transcendence of 58% which was like Western data [2, 26]. In this investigation, just 8 (8.6%) patients were >60 years old. Writing demonstrates 30% - 40% patients present with restricted malady, while 60% - 70% patients present with cutting edge disease [27]. In our accomplice, 59% of patients gave limited infection, while 41% gave propelled illness. Since the dominant part of patients had a place with low to low middle of the road gathering, treating these patients with R-CHOP did not give survival advantage in our investigation. The review nature and its little example estimate are the primary impediments of the examination.

CONCLUSION:

IPI remains an essential apparatus to anticipate survival. R-CHOP is the standard of consideration for CD20 positive NHL, yet in under-resourced nations CHOP alone might be utilized in okay patients, while R-CHOP can be utilized in the high-risk gathering. Further planned investigations are required to approve these outcomes.

REFERENCES:

1. Feugier P, Van Hoof A, Sebban C, Solal-Celigny P, Bouabdallah R, Fermé C et al. Long-term results of the R-CHOP study in the treatment of elderly patients with diffuse large B-cell lymphoma: a study by the Groupe d'Etude des Lymphomes de l'Adulte. *J Clin Oncol* 2005; 23:4117-26.
2. Pfreundschuh M, Kuhnt E, Trümper L, Osterborg A, Trneny M, Shepherd L et al. CHOP-like chemotherapy with or without rituximab in young patients with good-prognosis diffuse large-B cell lymphoma: 6-year results of an open-label randomized study of the MabThera International Trial (MInT) Group. *Lancet Oncol*. 2011; 12:1013-22.
3. Habermann TM, Weller EA, Morrison VA, Gascoyne RD, Cassileth PA, Cohn JB et al. Rituximab-CHOP versus CHOP alone or with maintenance rituximab in older patients with

- diffuse large B-cell lymphoma. *J Clin Oncol* 2006; 24:3121-7.
4. Ziepert M, Hasenclever D, Kuhnt E, Glass B, Schmitz N, Pfreundschuh M et al. Standard International prognostic index remains a valid predictor of outcome for patients with aggressive CD20+ B-cell lymphoma in the rituximab era. *J Clin Oncol* 2010; 28:2373-80.
5. Shenoy PJ, Malik N, Nooka A, Sinha R, Ward KC, Brawley OW et al. Racial differences in the presentation and outcomes of diffuse large B-cell lymphoma in the United States. *Cancer* 2011; 117:2530-40.
6. Cheson BD, Pfistner B, Juweid ME, Gascoyne RD, Specht L, Horning SJ et al. Revised response criteria for malignant lymphoma. *J Clin Oncol* 2007; 25: 579-86.
7. Daum S, Ullrich R, Heise W, Dederke B, Foss HD, Stein H et al. Intestinal non-Hodgkin's lymphoma: a multicenter prospective clinical study from the German Study Group on Intestinal non- Hodgkin's Lymphoma. *J Clin Oncol* 2003; 21:2740-6.
8. Vitolo U, Ferreri AJ, Zucca E. Primary testicular lymphoma. *Crit Rev Oncol Hematol* 2008; 65:183-9.
9. Sehn LH, Scott DW, Chhanabhai M, Berry B, Ruskova A, Berkahn L et al. Impact of concordant and discordant bone marrow involvement on outcome in diffuse large B-cell lymphoma treated with R-CHOP. *J Clin Oncol* 2011; 29:1452-7.
10. Fricke, Dörken B, Lenz G. The molecular biology of diffuse large B cell lymphoma. *Ther Adv Hematol* 2011; 2:369-79.
11. Shipp MA, Harrington DP, Anderson JR, Armitage JO, Brittinger G, Cabanillas F, et al. A predictive model for aggressive non- Hodgkin's lymphoma. The International Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma Prognostic Factors Project. *N Engl J Med* 1993; 329:987-94.
12. Sarkozy C, Coiffier B. Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma in the elderly: a review of potential difficulties. *Clin Cancer Res* 2013; 19:1660-9.
13. Green TM, Young KH, Visco C, Xu-Monette ZY, Orazi A, Go RS et al. Immunohistochemical double-hit score is a strong predictor of outcome in patients with diffuse large B-cell lymphoma treated with rituximab plus cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, vincristine, and prednisone. *J Clin Oncol* 2012; 30:3460-7.
14. Young KH, Leroy K, Møller MB, Colleoni GW, Sánchez-Beato M, Kerbauy FR. Structural profiles of TP53 gene mutations predict clinical outcome in diffuse large B-cell lymphoma: an international collaborative study. *Blood* 2008;

- 112:3088-98.
15. Alizadeh AA, Gentles AJ, Alencar AJ, Liu CL, Kohrt HE, Houot R et al. Prediction of survival in diffuse large B-cell lymphoma based on the expression of 2 genes reflecting tumour and microenvironment. *Blood*. 2011; 118:1350-8.
 16. Zhou Z, Sehn LH, Rademaker AW, Gordon LI, Lacasce AS, Crosby- Thompson A et al. An enhanced International Prognostic Index (NCCN-IPI) for patients with diffuse large B-cell lymphoma treated in the rituximab era. *Blood* 2014; 123:837-42.
 17. Fisher RI, Gaynor ER, Dahlberg S, Oken MM, Grogan TM, Mize EM et al. Comparison of a standard regimen (CHOP) with three intensive chemotherapy regimens for advanced non-Hodgkin's lymphoma. *N Engl J Med* 1993; 328:1002-6.
 18. Sehn LH, Donaldson J, Chhanabhai M, Fitzgerald C, Gill K, Klasa R, et al. Introduction of combined CHOP plus rituximab therapy dramatically improved the outcome of diffuse large B-cell lymphoma in British Columbia. *J Clin Oncol* 2005; 23:5027-33.
 19. Kaplan GL, Meier P. Nonparametric estimation from incomplete observations. *J Am Stat Assoc* 1958; 53: 457-81.
 20. Peto R, Pike MC. The conservatism of the approximation? (O-E) 2/E in the log-rank test for survival data or tumour incidence data. *Biometrics* 1973; 29: 579-84.
 21. Abid MB, Nasim F, Anwar K, Pervez S. Diffuse large B cell lymphoma (DLBCL) in Pakistan: an emerging epidemic? *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev* 2005; 6:531-4.
 22. Coiffier B, Lepage E, Briere J, Herbrecht R, Tilly H, Bouabdallah R et al. CHOP chemotherapy plus rituximab compared with CHOP alone in elderly patients with diffuse large-B-cell lymphoma. *N Engl J Med* 2002; 346:235-42.
 23. Swerdlow SH, Campo E, Harris NL, Jaffe ES, Pileri SA, Stein H, et al. World Health Organization Classification of Tumors of Hematopoietic and Lymphoid Tissues, IARC Press, Lyon 2008.
 24. Morton LM, Wang SS, Devesa SS, Hartge P, Weisenburger DD, Linet MS. Lymphoma incidence patterns by WHO subtype in the United States, 1992-2001. *Blood* 2006; 107:265-76.
 25. Armitage JO, Weisenburger DD. New approach to classifying non- Hodgkin's lymphomas: clinical features of the major histologic subtypes. Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma Classification Project. *J Clin Oncol* 1998; 16:2780-95.
 26. A clinical evaluation of the International Lymphoma Study Group classification of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma. Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma Classification Project. *Blood* 1997; 89:3909-18.
 27. Møller MB, Pedersen NT, Christensen BE. Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma: clinical implications of extranodal versus nodal presentation--a population-based study of 1575 cases. *Br J Haematol* 2004; 124:151-9.